

Integrating Traditional and Digital Marketing Strategy to Improve Customer Acquisition in Medical Device Distribution Company: Case Study of PT. UMI

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ABSTRACT: Digital innovation is the most important and beneficial strategy to address the need for expansion in health systems. But the goal goes much beyond merely updating the infrastructure. From a consumer standpoint, digital innovation must aim to radically alter the health care business model including medical device business. Over the past few years, medical device businesses have received aggressive, record-breaking investment. The Medical Device Company also greatly influenced by digitalization phenomenon which requires them to shift to adjust to new consumer behavior in Digital. PT. UMI is one of medical device company in Indonesia that has had an impact of this which has caused a significant decrease in sales in digital transformation era. PT. UMI as B2B business not only consider for digital but also the sales person in traditional marketing as key point to touch and interact with customers. A proposed marketing strategy with integration traditional and digital marketing is needed for this company to remain competitive in the midst of a digital transformation. The purpose of this research is to study PT. UMI's customer journey in business conditions and then determine the right digital strategy to increase PT. UMI sales and customer acquisition. Primary data collection is done by interviewing from the company side and from the consumer side to find out customer behavior. Based on interviews with PT. UMI's customers, several customer's frustration points were identified in PT. UMI's digital consumer journey: customers want to have flexibility to get information of products before purchasing, because customers need to spend a lot of time to waiting the customer service or sales person to answer the need. Exploration the products before buying it, customers want products with good quality, and customers want the convenience of knowing with the people who have experienced with the products. Through this study, the author reformulates the PT. UMI digital strategy with the 5A consumer journey framework to maximize every consumer touchpoint. The author brings the study to answer two main problems, first to build a customer journey strategy that fits the PT. UMI target market, and second to create recommendations of the best integration for traditional and digital strategy for PT. UMI to make customer journeys in medical device company more engaged and seamless. The recommendation is to create the integration traditional and digital marketing strategy, utilizing customer experience in digital platform. Then, implement Live Chat Features on websites and whatsapp as a proposed digital marketing strategy for PT. UMI.

KEYWORDS: Digital Consumer Journey, Digital Marketing Strategy, 5As Framework, Traditional Marketing Strategy, Medical Device

INTRODUCTION

Today's trend of digital marketing is expanding quickly and is incredibly beneficial to business. Additionally, customer insight may be programmed to conduct marketing and discover the appropriate consumer. Additionally, it may encourage customers to participate in marketing campaigns and provide real-time monitoring of results like consumer traffic, sales, and comments. The choice of the company to employ digital marketing for various objectives will determine the outcome. Similar to how digital marketing is optional in the medical device sector, it may provide businesses an edge and reduce their expensive marketing budget. The medical device industry is highly specialized and complicated. Products and solutions that have the flexibility to support the ecosystem have an edge. Imagine a streamlined and uniform platform that provides a comprehensive perspective of a patient, streamlines interactions with patients in terms of transactions, communications, and engagement, while also making the best use of limited resources and preventing caregiver fatigue. PT UMI was established 2014 focusing on business activities in the marketing and trading of medical devices. PT UMI besides offering distribution services, it is also a provider of marketing services for medical devices for suppliers (Principal). PT. UMI is healthcare distribution company founded and headquartered in Jakarta, Indonesia. PT. UMI provides diagnostic solutions

(Reagents, instruments, software, services) which determine the source of disease and contamination to improve patient health and ensure consumer safety. PT. UMI should find the opportunity for digital marketing to create a new solution for medical device marketing. Business to business (B2B) companies such as PT. UMI need to have a good presence in digital as well as traditional marketing with a sales person. The impact of Digital and traditional marketing is quite a lot if the presence is effective such as a more streamlined marketing process, the company's credibility is formed, or if it is very good additional opportunities will emerge. Therefore, integration between traditional and digital marketing is needed to increase customer acquisition and optimize marketing budgets so as to increase sales revenue from the company.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several internal and external issues that the medical device sector must deal with. Costs of medical devices are under control thanks to governments and international health organizations [1]. Many businesses develop price-fighting goods with competitive general quality in light of the market's current policy [2]. The premium market, have the unique product. Some businesses utilize the same brand to gain from increased client awareness and the brand experience. Similarly, some businesses utilize the umbrella brand to distinguish between fighting and luxury products. Both are utilized to supply the goods at competitive pricing [3]. In digital transformation should consider both of traditional and digital strategy. Traditional marketing is a marketing strategy that involves conventional media. Even though digital media has taken over a large part of marketing, there are still many brands that utilize this traditional media for promotional purposes [4]. Digital platform that offers scalable integration of users, suppliers, and prosumers. By leveraging governance tools like rating systems and specifying the level of transparency [5]. Companies must be able to encourage customers to share their opinions about the items they use on social media and guide them there so they may engage with other users there to influence consumer purchase intentions [6]. The digital customer journey includes all of a customer's digital touchpoints with a brand and collects data such as basic digital consumer data, transaction information, browsing history across all devices, and digital customer support interactions [7]. Digital customer journey mapping may be used by brands to create a communication strategy that engages customers in a discussion. Following the business's digital customer journeys allows the brand to monitor existing and planned client journeys, as well as key touch points across multiple marketing channels. One corporate method is to create a strategic action plan based on the Customer Path Map throughout the Five A's is can be approach to PT. UMI to solve the challenge [8].

RESEARCH METHOD

Research is being in qualitative method. Problem are identified through secondary data from Management report and primary data from in-depth interview with selected customer to have wider perspective of problem. International published as a supporting the secondary data. Adoption & development strategy enlighten how company adopts selected digital technologies digital technologies and further development [9].

Table 1. List of respondent of PT. UMI Costumers

No.	Name	Occupation	Institution
1	dr. A Sp. PK	Clinical Pathologist	Hospital
2	dr. B Sp. MK	Clinical Microbiologist	Hospital
3	dr. C Sp.PK	Clinical Pathologist	Laboratory
4	dr. D Sp.MK	Clinical Microbiologist	Laboratory
5	dr. E Sp.PK	Clinical Pathologist	Laboratory
6	dr. F Sp.PK	Clinical Pathologist	Hospital
7	dr. G Sp.MK	Clinical Microbiologist	Hospital
8	dr. H Sp.PK	Clinical Pathologist	Hospital
9	dr. I Sp.PK	Clinical Pathologist	Laboratory
10	dr. J Sp.MK	Clinical Microbiologist	Laboratory
11	dr. K Sp.PK	Clinical Pathologist	Hospital
12	dr. L Sp. PK	Clinical Pathologist	Hospital

Source : Author 2023

Table 1. Explains the list of respondents in conducting In-depth Interview. In this research, interview is conducted in online interviews via online meeting platforms. This is adjusted to the conditions of the respondent of existing customer.

ANALYSIS

The author proposes a business solution based on interview with current customer to face the problem by developing a strategic action plan based on the framework customer route from marketing 4.0 by Philip Kotler, Hermawan Kertajaya, and Iwan Setiawan: "Customer Path Map Throughout Five A's." Based on interviews with PT. UMI's current customer, the author attempted to map out the PT. UMI customer journey using the Five A technique. At each customer touch point, the author attempted to discover what the customers' wishes and wants were, as well as what the brand might do to alleviate some of the customer's frustrations. The Five A approach where the PT. UMI customer journey approach will be detailed explained using the Five A approach and Five A concept will assist PT. UMI in building Marketing Digital materials on the promotional key Visuals, Content in Website, Engagement with Customer, and Website interactive chat [8].

Table 2. Interview Result

No.	Topic	Detail Topic	Respond Answer
1	Customer Touch Point	Traditional and digital platform preference	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Both of traditional and digital platform are important Digital platform for flexible to access.
2	Customer Journey	<p>Consumer touch point, consumer want and desire based on 5A Framework :</p> <p>Aware stage</p> <p>Appeal stage</p> <p>Ask stage</p> <p>Act stage</p> <p>Advocate stage</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Customer heard about PT. UMI products on social media, website, promotion on webinar event. Friend recommendation Seminars as face to face event Good specification and quality products Unique product Fast response of teams Good service and maintenance after sales service Competitive Price Need to engage with experience customer Conversation via media social Interaction with sales representative Need flexible and seamless platform for interaction Order via email to the company Order with sales representative help Buy online via e-catalogue Bundling program Free trial program Discount program Join marketing program

Source: Author 2023

From the result of the analysis conduct by the author will concentrate on enhancing two customer paths: 'Appeal' and 'Ask'. On 'Appeal' customer need to know the product from experience customer. On 'Ask' customer need flexible and seamless platform for interaction. However, 'Aware' and 'Advocate' are also vital to consider; customers have no complaints about how to locate sales representative of PT. UMI because their promotional messages are straightforward and available on website and social media to reach their target demographic. However, in the future, in order to preserve PT. UMI Brand Awareness, an activity to increase the 'Aware' path must be considered. As of now, brand awareness for PT. UMI exists, and the brand must prioritize initiatives that might lead to sales. For 'Advocate,' PT. UMI consumers already gladly share their product experience via social media, webinar, traditional event, but in the future, it is vital to build an effort that may broaden the reach of the product. The strategic action plan will explain the proposal for PT. UMI to attain its objectives through comprehensive action steps that specify how and when these activities will be done [8]. It takes the objective that has been chosen and adds the specifics required to transform idea into action. The author will split the two recommendations on enhancing the customer route on 'Appeal' and 'Ask' by establishing the action building blocks for each customer path for the recommendations.

Figure 1. Strategic Action Plan Framework for PT. UMI

Based on the aforementioned strategic action plan framework approach, the author will focus on providing recommendations for optimizing the Appeal and Ask customer route, which may affect customer satisfaction and, as a result, boost customers' buy intentions at the conclusion of the study.

To appeal to customers using a digital strategy with promote customer experience in using medical devices on PT. UMI website, consider the following steps:

1. Understand PT. UMI target audience: Gain a deep understanding of PT. UMI target audience, including healthcare professionals and patients who may be interested in PT. UMI medical devices. Understand their pain points, needs, and challenges to tailor PT. UMI digital strategy accordingly.

2. Develop a user-friendly website: Create a website that is easy to navigate and visually appealing. Ensure that the PT. UMI is intuitive, and information about PT. UMI medical devices is easily accessible. Use clear and concise language to explain the features and benefits of PT. UMI's products.
3. Provide detailed product information: Include comprehensive product descriptions, specifications, and images for each medical device PT. UMI offer. Highlight key features, technical specifications, and any unique selling points that differentiate PT. UMI's products from competitors.
4. Use multimedia content: Enhance the customer experience by incorporating multimedia content on PT. UMI website. Utilize videos, images, infographics, and interactive elements to explain the functionality and usage of PT. UMI medical devices. Showcase case studies or success stories to provide real-world examples of how PT. UMI's products have helped patients or healthcare professionals.
5. Offer product demos and simulations: If possible, provide interactive demos or simulations of PT. UMI medical devices. This can help customers understand how the device works and its potential impact on patient care. Simulations can be especially useful in showcasing complex procedures or the device's user interface.
6. Include customer testimonials and reviews: Highlight positive customer experiences and testimonials on PT. UMI website. Showcase feedback from healthcare professionals or patients who have used PT. UMI medical devices, emphasizing the benefits they have experienced. Customer testimonials add credibility and build trust in PT. UMI products.

Creating an digital brand community enables products to be understand what motivates PT. UMI consumers, as well as what they satisfied and dislike about the customer experience. It may be thought of as a platform for collecting all product evaluations, feedback forms, and social activities. As previously said, PT. UMI is still weak in the 'Ask' where buyers seek easy engagement with the brand or those who are already familiar with the products. The author recommends adding a 'Live Chat' option to the PT. UMI website so that customers may seek guidance in real time before deciding to generate purchase the products to e-commerce or sales representative.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the customer journey and digital strategy of PT. UMI, as a medical device distribution company in Indonesia, play crucial roles in enhancing customer experience and driving business growth. By implementing a well-designed customer journey focus on 'Appeal' and 'Ask', PT. UMI can effectively attract, engage, and retain customers throughout their entire interaction with the company. The digital strategy employed by PT. UMI enables the company to leverage digital technologies and platforms to reach a wider audience, build brand awareness, and facilitate seamless transactions. With the increasing adoption of digital channels by customers, PT. UMI's digital strategy allows them to stay competitive in the rapidly evolving market. Through effective digital marketing, PT. UMI can create targeted campaigns, personalized messaging, and valuable content to engage potential customers. By understanding customer needs and preferences, PT. UMI can tailor their digital presence to deliver relevant information and establish themselves as a trusted source of medical devices. Beside on digital strategy, PT. UMI as Business to Business (B2B) company should consider the traditional marketing. Integration of traditional marketing with sales person and digital strategy with focus on customer journey will increase acquisition of customer also increase sales revenue.

REFERENCES

1. Clemons, Eric K. 2018. *New Patterns of Power and Profit: A Strategist's Guide to Competitive Advantage in the Age of Digital Transformation*.
2. de Reuver, Mark, Carsten Sørensen, and Rahul C Basole. 2017. The digital platform: a research agenda. *Journal of Information Technology* 33 (2):124-135.
3. Evans, David S. 2012. Governing bad behavior by users of multi-sided platforms. *Berkeley Tech. LJ* 27:1201.
4. Evans, Peter C, and Annabelle Gawer. 2016. The rise of the platform enterprise: a global survey.
5. Gawer, Annabelle. 2014. Bridging differing perspectives on technological platforms: Toward an integrative framework. *Research policy* 43 (7):1239-1249.

6. Gerwe, Oksana, and Rosario Silva. 2018. Clarifying the sharing economy: conceptualization, typology, antecedents, and effects. *Academy of Management Perspectives* (In Press).
7. Ghazawneh, Ahmad, and Ola Henfridsson. 2013. Balancing platform control and external contribution in third-party development: the boundary resources model. *Information Systems Journal* 23 (2):173-192.
8. Butler, Brian S., Patrick J. Bateman, and Peter H. Gray. 2014. An Attraction-Selection-Attrition Theory of Online Community Size and Resilience. *MIS Quarterly* 38 (3):699-728.
9. Kotler, Philip, et al. 2017. *Marketing 4.0: Moving from Traditional to Digital*. Hoboken, New Jersey, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Cop.

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